

Family Types as Predictors of Family Stability in Anambra State of Nigeria. Implication for Family Well Being.

Umezulike Roseline Ekwutosi (PhD)¹, Vera Nkiru Nwadinobi (Ph.D)² & Afunugo Dorothy Mmaegbunam (Ph.D)³

¹Department of Educational Psychology/ Guidance and Counselling
Nwafor Orizu College of Education, Nsugbe, Anambra State
E-mail: roseumezulike@yahoo.com
08035705131

²Department of Educational Psychology/ Guidance and Counselling
Nwafor Orizu College of Education, Nsugbe, Anambra State
E-mail: kiru92007@gmail.com
08033463632

³Department of Educational Psychology/ Guidance and Counselling
Nwafor Orizu College of Education, Nsugbe, Anambra State
E-mail: dorammafunugo@yahoo.com
08035534622

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Abstract

This study investigated family types as predictors of family stability in Anambra State of Nigeria. The main purpose of the study was therefore to investigate how family types predicted family stability in Anambra State of Nigeria. The design of the study was ex-post facto design. In pursuance of the aforementioned objective two research questions were posed and two hypotheses were tested. A proportionate stratified random sampling technique was employed to select 748 respondents from Anambra State of Nigeria for the study. A structured 30 –item questionnaire which was duly validated by three experts was used to collect data. Data collected were analyzed using mean scores and standard deviation for the research questions and t-test for the hypotheses. The major findings of the study showed that there is a significant different between nuclear and extended family types on family stability. There was no significant difference between monogamous and polygamous family types on family stability. In other words family type predicted family stability in Anambra State. Based on the findings it was recommended among others that counselors should create awareness for married couples through workshops and seminars on how to adopt the nuclear type of family and make the best out of it.

Key words: Family, Predictor, Stability

Introduction

The family is one of the institutions that exist in a constant state of mutual interaction. It is the smallest social unit, yet the most fundamental institution in any society. It is the basic social

institution from which other institutions have grown. According to Minnet (2000) "Family is the basic unit of society. It is a group of people of various ages usually related by birth, marriage or adoption". She went further to say that members of a family feel that they have a special relationship with each other based on blood, affection, duty, shared experience and common interests. This special relationship is a knot that holds a family together making it the most suitable human society. The family is the institution through which socially approved coupling between man and woman takes place. It is the only institution in most, if not every society, recognized as qualified to carry out the roles of child bearing, and rearing as well as loving and caring for its members.

Action Health (2003) also defined the family as the arena in which virtually the entire range of human experiences can take place. These include love, tenderness, honesty, communal sharing, joy, happiness, poverty, deceit, jealousy, envy, violence, warfare, guidance and acceptance. Murdock in Onu (2004) defined family as a social group characterized by common residence, economic cooperation and reproduction. The family, he continued, includes adult of both sexes, two of whom at least maintain a socially approved sexual relationship and one or more owned or adopted children of the sexually cohabiting adults.

The African perspective of the family is slightly different from the western perspective. In the African context, and by extension, the Nigerian context, a family consists of the husband, wife, children and the extended families of the couple. Nwobi in Umezulike (2011) defined the family as a bio-social group, a network of persons intimately held together by a bond of social and kinship relationship or blood relationships. Nwobi goes on to say that in the Nigerian context, at least because of the phenomenon of extended family system, the family is made up of the married couple, their offsprings and immediate kit and kin, brothers and sisters of the bridegroom and his parents, relatives-in-laws, and any other dependant, so that the concept of nuclear families is a product of colonial experience in most parts of Africa. Following from the above, family in the context of this study can be defined as a group of people closely related by blood, sharing common residence and interests consisting at least of two adults of both sexes who maintain a socially approved sexual relationship and or one or more children of the sexually cohabiting adults.

Since counselling aims at helping people cope and adjust better with situations that are threatening to their existence in life and the assistance may be in the area of their emotions and feelings where they need assistance to make choices and decisions, it follows that such decisions rightly made could contribute greatly to the overall well being of the family (Adenuga, 2013).

Family stability is a state where there is low level of tension in the family between family members. Nwadinigwe and Anyama (2010) defined family stability as an adaptation between family members to a point where there is companionship and agreement on basic issues, values, affection, intimacy and accommodation of each other. A family can be said to be stable where family members develop a spirit of tolerance, love and consideration for one another which,

according to George (2002), bring about members' happiness and satisfaction. Hence, where there is happiness and contentment expressed by family members, such a family could be said to be stable. A stable family is one where there is minimized or near absence of open quarrel. Family instability is a state of permanent tension in the family. Family stability is synonymous with family well being. This is because family well being is defined as a contented state in which a group of people live together in spite of minor misunderstanding and challenges which they work together to overcome. When family well being occurs, individuals are collectively happy, healthy, satisfied and prosperous in all facets of life. Iloanya (2005) revealed that family instability on the other hand is the "break-up of a family unit, the dissolution or fracture of a structure of social roles that is, when one or more members fail to perform adequately their roles.

The researcher sees family instability as those unagreeable circumstances in the family. It is a state of struggle, disagreement and trial of strength between family members. Family instability arises when a demand for immediate change in the behaviour of one person is met with non-compliance. It also arises where there is a disagreement in the following areas – getting things done, expression of affection to or by spouse, sexual relations, fertility status, poor communication, unwillingness to discuss problems among family members, in-laws, problems of finance or spouse taking responsibilities.

Infact, family instability has characterized the family scene in Anambra State. Thus, Ifemeje (2008), found that increasing cases of family instability besiege social welfare homes in the State. According to her, the statistical data collected at Onitsha North local Government Area of Anambra State revealed that the social welfare unit handled 120 cases of marital problems and 14 cases of matrimonial conflicts between the years, 2003 and 2006. Furthermore, the Awka South local government social welfare office in Awka also mediated 90 marital problems and about 9 outright divorces between the years 2001 and 2005. It is believed, according to her, that this is an eye opener to the fact that there is actually an increase in the general rate of family breakdown in Anambra State but most couples avoid going to court for the dissolution of such unstable marriages, probably for the sake of the children of the marriage and the cultural background and social desirability fact which demand that women should be submissive to their husbands and families wanting to be seen as good or better than each other.

In Nigeria, family stability or instability may find explanation on the type of the family. Family type has to do with the structural arrangement of the family. Anyakoha (1991), defined family type as the formation or shape in which a group of persons united by ties of marriage, blood or adoption are arranged. From the discussion so far, the researcher sees family type as the total number of individuals living within a family at a given period, composed of the father, the mother, their children and relations. In the context of this work, family type refers to the structure of the family in terms of whether it is nuclear, extended, polygamous and monogamous.

The type of the family varies from society to society, but the basic family type are nuclear, extended, monogamous, polygamous families. The nuclear family comprises basically of the

father, the mother and their direct offspring, and sometimes their adopted children. It is the basic unit from where other forms of family develop. Thus, Adewuyi (2009), stated that the nuclear family comprises basically of the father, the mother and their children. One basic characteristic of this type of family is its closeness in terms of relationship among members, and more importantly, the lack of extended relations.

Contrasted with the nuclear family, is the extended family structure. This form of family consists of father, mother, wives, children, grandparents and other relatives. It is likely that in the extended family, relationship among members may not be as close as it is in the nuclear type. Given the anticipated closer relationship among members of the nuclear family, one question that arises is, would such families report higher level of stability? The result of the present study will show.

Another type of family structure commonly practiced in the area of study is monogamous family. Monogamous family is a family made up of a man, his wife and their children. This type of family arises from the marriage of a man to one wife. Thus, Olson and Defrain (2000), asserted that monogamous family is a type of family in which the household head/man or woman has only one mate. In contrast to the monogamous family is the polygamous type. The polygamous family is one in which a person has more than one spouse. Given that the polygamous families may bring with it diverse characteristics in terms of different wives and their children, will this type of family report lower levels of stability? Or will the competition likely to be engendered by competing house wives to please their husband bring about more stability?

Thus Esere (2005) posited that instability in family setting is a bane to societal peace and harmony. Family instability carries with it many consequences which can manifest in many ways. At the family level there is high level of indiscipline as no one is in control. In unstable families, it is everyone for himself as there is no recognized authority to control the family. The consequences of this will be nothing but chaos. Emotional stress which is expressed in unhappiness, sadness, worry, anger, boredom is also a feature of unstable family. The family may become isolated as none may want to interact with them. Because members of the family are unhappy, they try to vent this unhappiness through aggression.

Retrogression in school performance may also be an effect of family instability on the children. This is because children from unstable families may be going through psychological and emotional instability themselves. They hardly concentrate and are likely to play truancy. It is for this reason that Anagbogu (1997) stated that when the psychological needs of children in any marriage are not met mainly due to existing disagreement between spouses, the children become frustrated and easily pick up anti-social behaviours within and outside their immediate environment. Therefore, the instability of the family may rub off on the achievement of the products of that family (children).

In the larger society, instability in the family may manifest itself in many ways, for instance high crime rate, that is, robbery, arson, murder, suicide, cultism, drug addiction and prostitution. These are all social vices that destroy the individual and the society, yet instability in families as shown in an earlier study by Ifemeje (2008) is on the increase. Given the devastating impacts of instability on the individual and the society at large, there is every cause to isolate those factors that promote it while attempt must also be geared at determining those that promote stability. It is for this reason that the researcher was moved towards investigating the extent to which family type predicted family stability in Anambra State.

The main purpose of the study was to investigate how family type predicted family stability. Specifically, the study:

1. ascertained the difference between the family types (nuclear and extended) on family stability.
2. determined the difference between the family types (Monogamous and Polygamous) on family stability.

The study was guided by two research questions

1. What is the difference between the nuclear and extended family types on family stability?
2. What is the difference between the monogamous and polygamous family types on family stability?

Two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance were formulated to guide the conduct of the study.

1. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of nuclear and extended family type on family stability.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of monogamous and polygamous family types on family stability.

Method

An ex-post facto or casual comparative design was used to collect data for the study. The design enables the researcher to link some already existing effect or observation in some variables as causative agents. The subjects are already assigned to or classified into the various levels of variables whose effects are being investigated. In the present study, the variables in family – nuclear and extended, monogamous and polygamous, were already in existence at the time of study. The design is considered appropriate for the present study because the researcher cannot manipulate the independent variables. The study was carried out in Anambra state. Anambra state of Nigeria is bounded in the north by Benue state and Kogi, in the East by Enugu state in

the South by Imo state as in the West by Delta state. Anambra state has three senatorial zones. Anambra North, central and Anambra south. Each senatorial zone has seven local government areas giving a total of 21 local government areas for the state. The target population for this study is one hundred and sixty-nine thousand one hundred and ninety two (169,192) household derived from 21 local government areas of Anambra State of Nigeria. The sample for the study consisted 748 household heads selected through stratified proportionate sampling technique as follows: Anambra East 30; Awka South 42; Idemili North 86; Nnewi North 311; Onitsha North 252; Orumba South 27. The instrument used for data collection is the family stability scale (FSS) developed by the researcher. The instrument is organized under two sections. A & B. Section A of the instrument is on demographic information which captured family type. Section B is on family stability and it contains 30 items listed on a 4-point rating scale and the respondents were expected to tick in the appropriate column the extent to which they agreed or disagreed with the items in relation to their various families. The instrument was subjected to face and content validity by subjecting it to the scrutiny of three experts, two from marriage/family Counselling from University of Nigeria Nsukka, one from Measurement and Evaluation from Nnamdi Azikwe University Awka. These experts were very useful in making corrections leading to the expunging of some items and the instrument was recast as directed by them. To ensure reliability of the instrument a trial test was conducted to determine the reliability of the instrument. The instrument was administered to 20 household-heads randomly selected from nuclear, extended, monogamous and polygamous family types from Asaba which is outside the study area. The choice of the area was to avoid contamination from the main parent population. Data from the reliability test were used to compute for the internal consistency of the instrument. The internal consistency reliability estimate of the instrument was established using Cronbach Alpha and the result showed 0.93 for family type and 0.96 for family stability scale. The researcher employed the assistance of six (3) research assistants in the distribution of the instrument. An on-the-spot mode was employed to ensure maximum collection of the instrument. The data collected were analyzed descriptively using mean score, standard deviation t-test analysis. A mean of 2.50 and above was regarded as a bench mark for accepting a questionnaire item as factor as perceived by the respondents. The research questions were answered, using mean score and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested using t-test analysis.

Results:

The analysis of data on the research questions and hypotheses obtained from the instrument were presented in tables 1,2,3, and 4 as follows.

Research question 1: What is the difference between the family types (nuclear and extended) on family stability.

Table 1

Mean Scores and Standard Deviations of the Difference between the Family Types (nuclear and extended) on Family Stability.

Family Type	N	Mean	SD
Nuclear	283	2.61	.24
Extended	465	2.42	.16

Data on table 1 show the mean scores and standard deviations of nuclear and extended family types on family stability scale. The data show that respondents from the nuclear family type had a mean of 2.61 with a standard deviation of .24 on the family stability scale while those from the extended family type had a mean score of 2.42 with a standard deviation of .16. This result showed that the nuclear family type was more stable than the extended family type. The standard deviation is a measure of dispersion or variability from the mean. The lower standard deviation of the extended family type showed homogeneity in agreement, or that a greater number of the respondents agree on the issue or item raised than is the case with nuclear family type with a higher standard deviation.

Hypothesis I: There is no significant difference between the nuclear and extended family types on family stability.

Table 2

t-test Analysis of Nuclear or Extended Family Types on Family Stability.

Family Type	N	Mean	t-cal	t-crit	df	sig.	dec.
Nuclear	283	2.61	13.02	1.96	746	.05	sig.
Extended	465	2.42					

Data on table 2 show that there is significant difference between the nuclear and extended family types on family stability. This is shown by the calculated t value of 13.02 which is significant at .05 level of probability. The null hypothesis of no significant difference between the nuclear and extended family types on family stability is rejected as the difference is significant. The data therefore suggest that there is a significant difference between the nuclear and extended family types on family stability of the respondents is significant.

Research Question 2: What is the difference between the family types (monogamous and polygamous) on family stability?

Table 3

Mean Scores and Standard Deviation of the Difference between the Family Types (monogamous and polygamous) on Family Stability.

Family Type	N	Mean	SD
Monogamous	480	2.47	.21
Polygamous	268	2.53	.22

Data on table 3 show the mean scores and standard deviation of monogamous and polygamous family types on family stability scale. The data show that respondents from the monogamous family type had a mean of 2.47 with a standard deviation of .21 on the family stability scale while those from the polygamous family type had a mean score of 2.53 with a standard deviation of .22. This means that the polygamous family type had a higher level of stability than the monogamous family type. The smaller value of standard deviation of the monogamous family type is an indication that a greater number of the respondents agree on the issue or items raised than is the case with the polygamous family type with a slightly larger standard deviation.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the monogamous and polygamous family types on family stability.

Table 4

t-test Analysis on the Difference between Monogamous and Polygamous Family Types on Family Stability

Family Type	N	Mean	t-cal	t-crit	df	sig.	dec.
Monogamous	480	2.47					
			-3.65	1.96	746	.05	N.S.
Polygamous	268	2.53					

Data on table 4 shows that there is no significant difference between the monogamous and polygamous family types on family stability. This is shown by the calculated t-value of -3.65 which is not significant at .05 level of probability. The null hypothesis of no significant difference between the monogamous and polygamous family types on family stability is accepted. The data therefore suggest that the difference between the monogamous or polygamous family types on family stability is not significant.

Discussion

The issues in the research questions and hypotheses were jointly discussed for better inferences as well as to show the influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The discussion therefore was organized under the following sub-headings.

1. Difference between the family types (nuclear and extended) on family stability.
2. Difference between the family types (monogamous and polygamous) on family stability.

The crux of research question 1 and its accompanying hypothesis is the difference between the family types (nuclear and extended) on family stability. The responses to the research question and hypothesis are summarized in tables 1 and 2. The result of analysis show that the nuclear family type has a higher level of stability than the extended family type. This finding is in line with the work of Okeke(2005) which suggested that the extended family ties may drain resources such as living space, food parental attention from the children and that these ties may in some cases place the children at risk. This may contribute to family instability by creating a state of insecurity which in turn may bring disaffection leading to the breakup of such homes. This explained why Larson in Okeke (2005) said that high –risk students are more likely than other youths to live in homes with numerous relatives and non-relatives. Family instability will certainly be the result. However even with the seeming higher level of stability demonstrated in the nuclear family type, the wide disparity in the standard deviation also reveals a cautions sign. What this means is that a few nuclear family with higher levels of stability may have contributed to the higher level of the stability whereas, most of the nuclear family members may be groaning under the weight of instability.

The focus of research question 2 and hypothesis 2 was to find the difference between the family types (monogamous and polygamous) on family stability. The findings are summarized in tables 3 and 4. This finding contradicts Ndu (2000) who stated that polygamy has the potential for developing envy, aggressive behaviour, favoritism disregard for equity and fairness and other antisocial behaviours. This may be as a result of increased family counselling practices, intensive enlightenment campaigns against infighting in families, be they monogamous or polygamous, presence of adequate resources to cater for the family, healthy competition among siblings, cordial relationship between husband and wife or wives as well as a suitable leadership style of the household head. The disparity in the standard deviation could also have contributed to the polygamous families experiencing stability. Maisamari (2006) also stated in her work that in Africa, especially Nigeria, men have continued the practice of polygamy resulting to divorce and desertion of families and family members. The finding of the present study has posed a challenge to this assertion. Hence, it is not difficult nowadays to find stable polygamous families or unstable monogamous families that show signs of disintegration. As rightly observed by Nwoke (2004), children need not only clothes and food but also emotional involvement and interaction with all the parents.

Implications for family well being

The implications of this study for family well being, based on the findings are as follows: Family and marriage counsellors should stress, during counselling of couples, that couples should lean more towards the nuclear family type than the extended family type since the former tends to be more stable. No doubt, a family can be said to be stable where family members develop a spirit of tolerance, love and consideration for one another which, according to George (2002) brings about members happiness and satisfaction and overall well being. The fewer the members of a family unit, the more possible it is for this situation to arise. However, this does not mean that the dependents of a couple should not be taken care of. These dependents should get accommodated outside the nuclear family and yet get all the support and encouragement they need from the couple. This practice will help reduce the incidence of many individuals residing in the matrimonial home and having to struggle with the inadequate accommodation and lean resources of the family in question.

The polygamous family type was found, by this study, to be more stable than the monogamous family type, contrary to the usual expectation. The role of the counsellor here is to create public awareness through mass media that people who have found themselves in the polygamous family type, with understanding and cooperation among its members, can still achieve family stability and well being. The members of such a family type may find out that, provided there are sufficient resources, healthy competition and cooperation among them will make for progress and prosperity. This is more so when there is cogent reason for establishing such family type. With the increased insistence of the churches and religious organizations on one man one wife, the polygamous family type is on the decrease, but wherever it is found, the impression should not be given that, the polygamous family type is prone to instability, infighting and disarray.

Conclusion

This study investigated family type as predictors of family stability in Anambra State of Nigeria and the implication for family well being. The importance of this study lies in the fact that the family units make up the entire society and the overall well being of these family units determines the well being of the society in particular and the nation in general. Families are society's most enduring basis for raising children, caring for family members, providing and receiving love, means and support, and for transmitting values, culture, language and traditions between generations. It follows therefore that when such an important and indispensable entity is unstable, the well being of its members is at stake and the larger society bears the brunt of this situation. In order to save the society and its members, pre marriage and family counselling should not only be given to married and intending couples but to everyone.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. The usual impression that the polygamous family type is always unstable should be discarded. Counsellors and government should create public awareness on the importance of living together as family rather than discriminating on the basis of different mothers and wives.
2. There should be compulsory and proper pre-marriage and marriage counselling for intending couples and those already in it by marriage counsellors. To this end, Guidance and Counselling Centres should be established in localities where they will be accessible to the generality of the people.

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